

MODELING THE METHODOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF TEACHERS OF TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION

Associate Professor of the Department of Technological Education and Library Science,
Kokand State University, PhD,
M.Kh. Ikramova

Annotation: This article presents ideas on the modeling of the methodological activities of teachers of technology education and their current state. Educating the younger generation requires great responsibility and knowledge from educators. The methodological activities of the teacher are of great importance in the development of science.

Keywords: technology, education, teacher, methodology, activity, demand, modeling, technology, development, knowledge, skills, qualifications, science, science.

The changes currently taking place in the education system, associated with new realities in socio-economic and political life, the desire for a global educational space, the emergence of new information technologies force teachers of Technology Education to think about new ways to break out of the traditional framework of training, to look for new approaches to the educational process. The stage of mastering the profession is an important stage in preparing a person for independent life. It is during their studies in higher educational institutions that future teachers of Technology Education form basic ideas about the content and characteristics of the profession being mastered, the formation of primary professional skills and abilities, and the development of professionally significant qualities of the individual occur.

The most general goals of education in the process of technological education include the following:

- effective adaptation of students to dynamically changing socio-economic conditions and ensuring comprehensive socialization;
- formation of special knowledge, skills and abilities, and development of professionally significant qualities of a specialist.

The educational process should be designed in such a way that as a result it is possible to train a teacher of technological education who can work in a new way, who can be a subject of pedagogical activity, therefore, the following should be formed in the process of professional and methodological preparation:

- pedagogical guidelines for the development of the student;
- ability to design one's own pedagogical activity;
- ability to reflect on one's own pedagogical experience.

To achieve the goals of education, content and technologies that meet the specifics of the training of a teacher of technological education should be formed.

The content of education is the most important component of the process of training a teacher of Technology Education. No matter how diverse and effective the forms, methods and means of education are, no matter how good the educational technology is, if the content of education is incorrectly defined, it will not be possible to ensure the quality of training of specialists.

The content of education is a category that determines the requirements for the final result of educational preparation - professional and methodological activities. It includes requirements for the knowledge, skills and abilities of graduates, their general level of knowledge, breadth of outlook, level of intellectual development, the formation of needs and interests in learning, readiness for independent development of professionally important qualities. These requirements are determined by society, depend on the level of its development and change with the development of science, culture, production, society.

The content of education is the goal that an educational institution should achieve for each future specialist.

In forming the content of the educational content of a technology education teacher, we have determined the composition of knowledge, skills and abilities, and professionally important qualities that students should possess in the process of learning. In forming the content of the educational content, we have determined the composition of educational information presented to students in the form of a set of tasks, tasks and exercises and didactic units (educational elements) aimed at the formation of appropriate skills and abilities, as well as professionally important qualities.

In forming the content of technology education, contradictions arise between the subject (subject-related) nature of education and the full, integrated nature of professional and methodological activities, between the theoretical nature of education and the reality of professional practical activities.

In the process of training, students learn and master the basic laws and regularities, principles, classifications and properties expressed in the form of theoretical rules. However, it is impossible to directly transfer them to professional and methodological practical activities; between theoretical rules and real practical activities there is practical knowledge that turns theoretical rules into practical recommendations. Practical recommendations can be given to students in a ready-made form, and then the knowledge will have a “planned” character. “Planning” burdens the nature of the content of training, making it narrower, more limited and temporary. Therefore, the most important problems in the formation of the content of education and the content of training are: choosing the most appropriate option of the necessary and sufficient knowledge, skills and abilities for their implementation in professional and methodological activities and the composition of the set of educational information issues and tasks corresponding to this option; determining the ratio and correspondence of the alternative of fundamental and practical training to the goals of education; determining the balance and correspondence between theoretical and practical training to educational goals.

The composition of knowledge necessary for the implementation of basic, professional and methodological activities can be interpreted in different ways. The following should be included in the category of necessary, along with sufficient, the following, which ensure the vertical growth and horizontal movement of a teacher of technological education:

- knowledge, skills and abilities;
- the ability to creatively express oneself in work;
- a reserve of knowledge, skills and abilities for making decisions in extreme situations when a specialist is forced to go beyond the limits of his duties;
- the ability to correctly assess his professional and methodological activities in the system of performing labor duties together with other people, to communicate with them in the process of regulating his own and their activities.

In the conditions of rapid development of technology, science and culture, professional knowledge related to specific working conditions is rapidly becoming obsolete and needs constant updating. It is practically impossible to get acquainted with all the educational technologies, materials, machines and mechanisms available in circulation even in one specific production. At the stage of formation of the labor market, the possibility of professional mobility of specialists increases, which requires expanding their specializations. It is important to select the most important information from a large amount of information, thus forming a system of methods of activity and knowledge for students so that they can use them rationally in various situations, that is, to provide them with fundamental education.

Fundamentalization of education represents a set of the most important and invariable content that can be followed in practical activities. Here we are talking about knowledge of the basic principles and laws that allow us to correctly assess the possibilities of applying newly acquired knowledge. This is not about the dominance of general or general professional

disciplines, but about identifying the most important knowledge for professional use in specialized disciplines, the principles of their selection, the possibility of their interchangeability, etc.

At the same time, an important problem in the formation of the content of professional and methodological training is to determine the appropriate ratio of theoretical and practical components in each subject.

The problem of developing and improving the process of training teachers of technology education is relevant in ensuring coherence and continuity with general secondary educational institutions. The content of technology education is formed on the basis of the following principles:

- personal-activity approach;
- professional expediency;
- adaptation of the content of education based on priority technologies;
- humanization of education;
- integration of engineering and pedagogical knowledge;
- compliance of the content of education with the nature and content of engineering-pedagogical activities.

Among the types of activities performed by a teacher of technology education, the following can be distinguished:

- professional and methodological training as both theoretical and practical training;
- extracurricular educational work in the educational-production group of students, possibly as a class leader or production training master;
- community work in the pedagogical team and in the student community, in dormitories, etc.;
- production-technological activities on the organization of students' production labor;
- marketing and entrepreneurial activities on the organization of students' production labor;
- ensuring the work regime in the educational institution of the educational group;
- improving one's qualifications and level of education;
- vocational guidance of students;
- initial test-experimental activities of a research nature.

In conclusion, it can be said that methodological activities are of particular importance in the formation and development of students' knowledge in the field of Technology. If the teacher is methodologically developed, then he will be able to achieve great results in imparting knowledge to students and teaching them a profession.

List of used literature

1. Хонбобоев, Х. О., Икромова, М. Х., & Икромов, М. А. Х. (2016). Та'limda axborot texnologiyalarni qollashning oziga xos xususiyatlari. Молодой ученый, (3-1), 21-22.
2. MUBINAKHON, I., & ANASKHON, I. M. The Importance of Using the Ict to Increase the Efficiency of Education. JournalNX, 7(1), 106-108.
3. Ikramova, M. (2022). SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF USING MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS IN TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS OF TECHNOLOGY. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning, 3(9), 1-4.
4. Isaqova, Z., M. Ikramova, and M. Abdusamatova. "TO EDUCATE STUDENTS TO BE SMART, POLITE, WELL-MANNERED, INTELLIGENT AND PHYSICALLY HEALTHY IN THE PROCESS OF LABOR EDUCATION." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 9.12 (2021): 868-870.
5. Ikramova, M. Kh. "USE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN" TECHNOLOGY" CLASSES." Open Access Repository 8.11 (2022): 116-120.

6. Ikramova, M. Kh. "PECULIARITIES OF USING DIGITIZED EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN" TECHNOLOGY" CLASSES." Open Access Repository 9.11 (2022): 208-212.
7. Alimov, B., Isaqova, Z., Ikramova, M. X., & Bo'teyev, A. (2022). DIDACTIC SHAPT-SHAPOITLAPI OF PIVOJLANTIP OF THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE TEACHER OF THE SCIENCE OF" TECHNOLOGY". Open Access Repository, 9(11), 328-333.
8. Gulyamov, K. M., and M. H. Ikramov. "Development of artistic and creative abilities of future teachers of fine arts through computer graphics." JournalNX 7.06 (2021): 95-99.
9. Xakimjonog, Ikromov Muhammad Anasxon. "BO 'LAJAK TASVIRIY SAN'AT O 'QITUVCHILARIGA "MUHANDISLIK KOMPYUTER GRAFIKASI" FANINI O 'QITISH JARAYONIDA ULARNING BADIY-IJODIY QOBILIYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK SHART-SHAROITLARI." Conferencea (2023): 34-38.